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Executive Summary

HIT2GAP (Highly Innovative Building Control Tools Tackling the Energy Performance Gap) was an H2020 Innovation Action that spanned 2015 to 2019. The project involved 23 European partners and had a budget of approximately €9 million and funding of approximately €7 million. It responded to the EeB-07-2015 (New tools and methodologies to reduce the gap between predicted and actual energy performances at the level of buildings and blocks of buildings). As such it is part of the Energy Efficiency in Buildings Public Private Partnership and supports the H2020 pillar of Industrial Leadership and Activity Line of Technologies enabling energy-efficient systems and energy-efficient building with a low environmental impact.

This report provides select public information at project closure. The information intends to inform the reader in a synthetic way how the consortium framed the problem, how it positioned itself, what it achieved and how it will go about exploiting the results it produced.

HIT2GAP tackled the challenge that the buildings often do not perform as intended with respect to energy consumption. This can result from errors in design, construction, commissioning or operation. The focus of the HIT2GAP project was on the operational phase where errors are most often caused by faulty equipment, setpoint errors, non-optimal operational schemes, and errors in human behaviour (with respect to energy consumption). It did this through developing a middleware platform that can connect to building information provided typically by a building management system and augmented by external sensors (IoT, dedicated meters, weather stations, occupancy counters, etc). Once collected, normalized, pre-processed and stored in a database, modules dedicated to perform specific functions were able to access this database and provide actionable information to building stakeholders. What is unique in this approach is that modules can be developed by 3rd party developers, they can connect to the middleware, and they can exchange information with other modules making new datasets and combined analytics possible. It is a builder's platform, not unlike the iPhone which empowered developers worldwide. It is deliberately Open Source and, in this way, others do not have to recreate the core functionalities of the middleware but can instead build upon it to create their own building energy management system.

Figure 1. BEMServer connecting buildings, modules, users and occupants

The middleware is called BEMServer (Figure 1). It is the world's first open source project dedicated to building energy management and parallels a successful open source project in the building information modelling domain (BIM) called BIMserver to facilitate branding and the attraction of

developers. Using the BEMServer, modules can work together and take advantage of outcomes coming from other modules to improve building performance (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Modules using and exchanging information in the BEMServer CORE.

Open source is a deliberate exploitation decision. Many are not aware, but open source software is a part of most computing systems we touch every day and most proprietary products and their producers (even now Microsoft and IBM) are embracing that parts of their products build on open source backbones. As such, BEMServer is positioned to take leadership as the backbone for building management solutions as they concern the operational phase of the building.

The HIT2GAP project closes with 23 exploitable results. Four relate to the BEMServer platform, twelve to the developed modules, three to supporting technologies, two to knowledge and IP, and two to services. The key exploitable result is the BEMServer which is software downloadable on GitHub and which is supported by a webpage, marketplace where modules can be downloaded (free or for purchase depending on the module), and presence on social media for marketing and communication. In addition to this central result, each result has an exploitation vision, several which are commercial and already generating sales. To see where BEMServer and its market place is today at any point when reading this document, go to www.bemserver.org. To download the code and readme files, go to <https://github.com/HIT2GAP-EU-PROJECT/BEMServer>. To follow our journey on social media, go to <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/bemserver/>. To watch short video of what it is all about, go to <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NFAik08n3C8>.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This report informs the reader of the main results of the HIT2GAP project and the exploitation plan for those results. To put those results into context, macro level market analysis information and market landscape information are also provided. We hope that readers of this report don't stop here but instead go to the BEMServer webpage and BEMServer open source project to see where we are today – and to join us.

1.2 Methodology

This report is intentionally simple. We provide the market framework in Chapter 2, present our results in Chapter 3, and document our plans for the future in Chapter 4. Along the way, we share lessons learned and how to frame the challenges and opportunities we faced.

Although simple, behind the report and the results is a four-year research effort of solution design, development, implementation, and validation combining the skills and effort of 23 partner organizations. During the project, the BEMServer was piloted on four buildings. The results from those implementations and all public reports from the HIT2GAP project are available on the project webpage (www.hit2gap.eu).

Behind this report on exploitation activities, there is the process of innovation management that occurred continuously along the duration of the project. These activities involved exploitation workshops, IPR workshops, value proposition design processes, business modelling, market analysis and replication planning at the individual, joint and consortium levels.

1.3 Abbreviation list

BEM	Building Energy Modelling
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BMS	Building Management System
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
FDD	Fault Detection & Diagnosis
FOSS	Free and Open Source
FM	Facility Manager
IEQ	Indoor Environmental Quality
OS	Open Source
USGBC	US Green Building Council

2 Market Analysis and Positioning

BEMServer is a platform that is open source within the domain of intelligent buildings.

2.1 Intelligent and Sustainable Buildings

Actionable insights from real time data is a driving force behind most technological trends in the built environment. These trends include Digitalization, the Internet of Things, Digital Twin, Smart Cities as well as Big Data, Cloud Computing, Artificial Intelligence, and Intelligent Digital Mesh as it applies to the built environment. Intelligent buildings can result in smarter and more efficient building operation and serve as a validation energy simulation models.

An Intelligent Building Market is the integration of building, technology, and energy systems. Building automation systems include building automation, life safety, telecommunications, user systems, and facility management systems. Intelligent buildings deliver actionable information about a building or space inside a building to permit the building owner or occupant to manage the building or space. The global intelligent building market was valued at \$ 12,371 million in 2017, and is projected to reach \$ 42,649 million by 2024, growing at a CAGR of 19.6% from 2018 to 2024. The global intelligent building market is currently dominated by key players such as Honeywell, ABB, Cisco Systems, Inc., Delta Controls, Honeywell International Inc., Intel Corporation, Johnson Controls, Legrand, Schneider Electric, Siemens AG, and United Technologies Corporation¹.

Figure 3. Intelligent building market, reproduced from Allied Market Research¹

¹ <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/intelligent-building-market>

Figure 4. Intelligent building market by Type, reproduced from Allied Market Research¹

Our interest in the intelligent building market is to reduce the energy performance gap in the operational phase of buildings. One image of the performance gap across select phases of the building life cycle is shown in Figure 5. From this study, it is reported that the operational phase contributes most to the energy performance gap and that most errors/faults can be managed through fault identification, energy management and changes in user behaviour. Where instead errors cannot be corrected during the operational phase due to systemic problems in design (such as thermal bridges) or errors in construction (such as non-sealed window frames), analysis and identification can facilitate improvement in processes for future buildings or correction actions for existing buildings (insulation / sealing).

Figure 5. Energy Performance Gap²

² The Performance Gap, Causes and Solutions, ARUP, Green Construction Board Buildings Working Group Final Report, 4 March 2013 available at www.greenconstructionboard.org

Performance and sustainability are two terms whose meaning continues to evolve. More and more, performance is expanding to include occupant comfort, productivity and wellness. More and more, sustainability is expanding to include circularity and end of life. Recently launched sustainability protocols such as WELL³ or the LEVELS⁴ framework address exactly these topics. Sustainability protocols are also moving from design-based to performance-based (e.g. certified by results underpinned by data). To implement this, the USGBC now requires data reporting via a platform called ARC⁵.

The connection with HIT2GAP and the resultant BEMServer is that pathways to the market will not only be energy efficiency but also performance and sustainability. Decision makers will consider these aspects and corporate social responsibility is part of the equation. The results already include modules involving indoor environmental quality (IEQ) and human behaviour. We can anticipate that future developers will create new modules whose purpose is as of today not identified. This is a core strength and competitive advantage of the BEMServer. It is free and fast to adapt to future needs and requirements.

2.2 Open Source

The project made a deliberate choice to publish the BEMServer code as Open Source. The decision was not immediate, and the decision process included the consideration of proprietary options. The end decision to be OS is significant. The main foreground of the project is available to developers worldwide. Instead of its future development being limited to the consortium partners or constrained to the timeline of the project, it is free to grow in new directions. That is not to state that it can be left to develop by its own. To the contrary, leadership and maintenance of an OS project is a set of work and tasks in itself.

It was not taken for granted that all researchers working in HIT2GAP or that all readers of this document will be familiar with software licensing and how decisions related to licensing might affect future exploitation and the development of an overall exploitation or business strategy for current or future collaborators. Some background is included here.

A software license grants authorization to use software under certain terms and considerations specified by the license type. In general, there are two main types of software licenses: **Proprietary** and **Free and Open Source Software (FOSS)**⁶. Software is protected by **Copyright** in Europe (and many other countries). Copyright is a legal right that grants the creator of an original work exclusive rights to determine whether, and under what conditions, this original work may be used by others. The license is the tool to enact and enforce this legal right. One view of software licensing in the context of copyright is provided in Figure 6⁷.

Figure 6. Software licensing in the context of copyright

³ <https://www.wellcertified.com/>

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/levels-common-eu-framework-core-sustainability-indicators-office-and-residential-buildings-part-3>

⁵ <https://arcskoru.com>

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Software_license accessed 16 Oct 2018.

⁷ By shaddim / Mark Webbink - Public Domain, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=45955580>

2.2.1 Proprietary Software Licenses

In a proprietary license, the publisher grants the use of one or more copies of software under an end-user license agreement (EULA), but ownership of those copies remains with the software publisher. The EULAs is used to include terms which define the uses of the software, such as the number of installations allowed or the terms of distribution and the end user cannot use the software without accepting these terms and conditions.

Common licensing models include per single user, per user in a discounted volume approach, per dongle (e.g. able to be used by one user on any device), per work station, per server, per site, per project or per company. Licenses may be time based (e.g. annual) or perpetual. Software licensing may include maintenance to incorporate the concept of updates. Maintenance may also include specific levels of technical support.

Proprietary refers to ownership and does always mean for money. There are freeware and shareware proprietary offerings (Figure 7⁸).

Related to the BEMServer and its marketplace, 3rd party module developers may elect a proprietary licensing approach.

2.2.2 Free and Open Source Software

Free and open-source software is software that can be classified as both Free software and Open-source software. This means that, anyone is freely licensed to use, copy, study, and change the software in any way, and the source code is openly shared so that people are encouraged to voluntarily improve the design of the software. This is in contrast to proprietary software, where the software is under restrictive copyright licensing and the source code is usually hidden from the users.⁹ Although there is nearly a complete overlap between the concepts, the curators of the terms disagree on certain aspects. In specific, Free Software claims to be motivated by the social considerations (e.g. freedom to create, improve and share). Open source is sometimes considered a preferred development approach (e.g. to save resources).

Figure 8 Software under various licensing schemes according to the Free Software Foundation

As defined by the Free Software Foundation (FSF), **Free Software** is software that ensures that the end users have freedom in using, studying, sharing and modifying that software. The term "free" is used in the sense of "free speech," not necessarily "free of charge." Free software should adhere to four freedoms¹⁰:

- The freedom to run the program as you wish, for any purpose (freedom 0).

⁸ <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=46544815>

⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Free_and_open-source_software accessed 16 October 2018

¹⁰ <https://www.fsf.org/> accessed 16 October 2018

- The freedom to study how the program works, and change it so it does your computing as you wish (freedom 1). Access to the source code is a precondition for this.
- The freedom to redistribute copies so you can help your neighbor (freedom 2).
- The freedom to distribute copies of your modified versions to others (freedom 3). By doing this you can give the whole community a chance to benefit from your changes. Access to the source code is a precondition for this.

As defined by the Open Source Initiative (OSI)¹¹, **Open Source Software** is released under a license in which the copyright holder grants users the rights to study, change, and distribute the software to anyone and for any purpose. Open-source software may be developed in a collaborative public manner. Open source software is freely accessible.

Proponents of FOSS software argue the following benefits: increased use and ease of attaining early adopters, lower costs of development and marketing, increased flexibility and greater innovation, greater reliability due to more developers working together, faster development and absence of commercial pressures that can degrade software qualities and sharing of the maintenance efforts.

Open source licenses fall within two categories of license types¹².

- **Copyleft Licenses:** Copyleft is the practice of using copyright law to offer the right to distribute copies and modified versions of a work and requiring that the same rights be preserved in modified versions of the work. Any works derived from a work with a copyleft license must themselves be copyleft when distributed and as such are considered protective or reciprocal. The most common example of a copyleft license is the **General Public License (GPL)** and its various versions.
- **Permissive licenses:** Permissive licenses are essentially non-copyleft licenses which means that they typically allow licensees to use, distribute and modify the licensed material, for almost any purpose, including distributing the licensed material as part of a proprietary-licensed project. Two common examples of permissive licenses are the **MIT license** and the **BSD license**.

There are many license types that fall into these two categories and many references online. The homepage of one interesting website/resource is shown in Figure 9¹³.

¹¹ <https://opensource.org/> accessed 16 October 2018

¹² <https://www.slideshare.net/vharshana/open-source-licences-35614097> accessed 18 October 2018.

¹³ <https://choosealicense.com/> accessed 18 October 2018.

Choose an open source license

An open source license protects contributors and users. Businesses and savvy developers won't touch a project without this protection.

Which of the following best describes your situation?

I need to work in a community.

Use the [license preferred by the community](#) you're contributing to or depending on. Your project will fit right in.

If you have a dependency that doesn't have a license, ask its maintainers to [add a license](#).

I want it simple and permissive.

The [MIT License](#) is short and to the point. It lets people do almost anything they want with your project, including to make and distribute closed source versions.

[Babel](#), [.NET Core](#), and [Rails](#) use the MIT License.

I care about sharing improvements.

The [GNU GPLv3](#) also lets people do almost anything they want with your project, *except* to distribute closed source versions.

[Ansible](#), [Bash](#), and [GIMP](#) use the GNU GPLv3.

What if none of these work for me?

My project isn't software.

[There are licenses for that](#)

I want more choices.

[More licenses are available](#)

I don't want to choose a license.

[Here's what happens if you don't](#)

Figure 9. Homepage from www.choosealicense.com

2.2.3 Open Source Buildings Landscape

A key moment in the project was the decision to parallel in several ways what BIMserver has done. BIMserver is a platform and an open source software in the field of BIM (Building Information Modelling). It is based on the BIM open standard IFC, that allows information and file exchange between different software and tools. The platform acts as software core to develop and link different tools and development projects in the field of BIM. It's not a fileserver. Indeed, data are interpreted and stored as objects in a specific database. The core of the platform software is open source and it is published with a GNU project free licences as project software in the framework of GNU free operating system software, as *GNU Affero General Public License*, *GNU General Public License*, *GNU Lesser General Public License* (www.gnu.org). TNO is the curator of BIMserver. It was launched as the first "cloud" system for BIM in 2008 and since that time, it has become the leader in open BIM worldwide with over 100,000 downloads per annum. Its references include use by the US Federal Integrated Services connecting the US Department of Défense, NASA, the Army Corps of Engineers and others). TNO was approached in its early years by proprietary BIM solution providers for a potential buyout but they declined seeing that there was a greater value in remaining independent and open which also matched their core values as a research institution. The landing page for BIMserver is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. BIMserver home page (www.bimserver.org)

The rationale to parallel BIMserver (by choosing the name BEMServer and linking to them) has several uses. First, BEMServer will potentially benefit from name recognition/branding. Second, their lessons learned are already accelerating the BEMServer OS project. Third, hopefully this will attract more developers to the BEMServer project and fourth, linking BIM and BEM is an opening field of activity with plenty of room for innovation potential.

Open Source Projects in the Building Landscape

With the decision to launch BEMServer as an Open Source project, we began to consider in a wider perspective, what is the community/movement we are joining, apart from BIMserver, what is happening in the OS community in the buildings sector and how can we benefit from OS developments already complete. This is in part need based. The BEMServer must connect to building BMS to receive the data it needs to do its job. In general, the HIT2GAP project has used proprietary software to make those connections. If that capability can be replicated via OS options, then the cost of deploying BEMServer on building projects will decrease and its use will increase.

The result of this OS in buildings landscaping exercise is shown in Table 1. It is a result attained in the HIT2GAP project of working with various OS experts in the field and cannot be found otherwise online. It is not assumed to be complete but is a starting point. The landscape is divided into 4 clusters. Device, Building, City and Region. Ideally, these scales/clusters should be compatible so that data can be easily linked between them. In reality, that is not perfectly the case. In total, 18 OS projects are identified. Most are active. Several are dormant. 8 OS projects are at the building level and of these, BEMServer is the only one targeting BEMS.

As a last note on the OS market landscape, during the project a significant event occurred. IBM bought the open source software distributor RedHat for \$34 billion making it the largest deal of its kind to date. The CEO of IBM (Ginni Rometty) had a series of interesting remarks in her press conference surrounding the event¹⁴:

"There's a trillion-dollar market in front of us. Clients have moved 20% of their applications to the cloud, but it is pretty much the cost-based easy stuff. 80% is in front of them and that is where Red Hat and IBM together can now be the #1 hybrid cloud provider. That's what you need for the next 80%. You need hybrid and you need to manage multiple clouds. Our clients want open technologies so with this acquisition we are now the open answer vs. all the proprietary cloud providers out there."

¹⁴ <https://www.redhat.com/en/about/press-releases/ibm-closes-landmark-acquisition-red-hat-34-billion-defines-open-hybrid-cloud-future>

Table 1. Landscape of Open Source Projects in the Building Sector

Project name	Scale	Has a data model	Building description in model	IFC integration	Field connection – BMS protocols	Field connection - IoT	Status/Comments
BEMServer www.bemserver.org NBK	Building	Yes. Based on linked data - BEMOnt	Based on building description in IFC/BOT	Yes. Can extract data from IFC to populate the data model	No.	Not tested.	Initiating. Designed for monitoring tertiary buildings, or at least big buildings with many equipment. For small simple residential building use other solution.
Fiware https://www.fiware.org/ FIRWARE Foundation	Multiscale	Yes. Full Linked Data, based on an ETSI standard. Extensive use of the SAREF model.	Yes, but only building (no lower level description - floor, space...)	No (apparently)	No (apparently). Supported protocols seem restricted to u120, mqtt, lwm2m, http, websocket, onem2m, sigfox, lora, nb-iot, ec-gsm-iot, lte-m, cat-m, 3g, grps	Yes.	Large active community with big actors. Designed for Smart Cities, Smart Energy, Smart Industry, Smart Agrifood: quite generic. Handles IoT.
OM2M https://www.eclipse.org/om2m/ LAAS-CNRS	Device	Does not seem like.	No. Only sensors (exposed on REST APIs)	No	Not apparently	Yes (oneM2M and SmartM2M standards)	Good contribution level up until 2018. Potentially dormant. IoT platform
sensiNact https://wiki.eclipse.org/SensiNact CEATech List	Region	Apparently not	Apparently not	no	Apparently not (LoRa, Zigbee, IEEE 802.15.4, Sigfox, enOcean, MQTT, XMPP, NGSI, HTTP, CoAP)	Yes	Gateway for smart cities
OpenMUC https://www.openmuc.org/ Fraunhofer Institut for Solar energy	Region	Apparently not	No (not in Javadoc)	No	Yes (Modbus TCP / Modbus, RTU / Modbus RTU/TCP, IEC 61850, IEC 60870-5-104, IEC 62056-21, DLMS/COSEM, KNX, M-Bus (wired), wireless M-Bus, eHz meters/SML, REST/JSON, SNMP, CSV)	No (to my knowledge)	Small (7 developers) but some very large actors (SIEMENS) Last comment 8 mo. ago A gateway for proprietary protocols in the smart home and smart energy domain.

Project name	Scale	Has a data model	Building description in model	IFC integration	Field connection – BMS protocols	Field connection - IoT	Status/Comments
BIMServer http://bimserver.org/ TNO	Building	open BIM standards like IFC, COBie, Collada, CityGML, etc. no overarching mapping ontology	IFC	Yes	Yes (limited like soap, json)	Yes (limited like soap, json and protocol buffers)	Active. 15 Contributors. An open and stable software core to build reliable BIM software tools. Performance of serialization and visualization are key concerns for scalable heterogeneous content
BrickSchema https://brickschema.org/#home Multiple stakeholders, EU commissioned	Building	In essence, it is a flexible data modelling approach using semantic web technologies	HVAC, Lighting, Electrical, Spatial, sensors, control relationships, sequential relationships	Alignment with IFC	BMS point dumps	Schema incorporates IoT part	Active. 6 Contributors. A data schema for incorporating different elements for a smart building. With several tools developed specifically for this schema.
Open Climate Workbench https://climate.apache.org/ Apache software foundation	Region	Does not seem like.	No	No	Not apparently	Not apparently	Active. 23 Contributors. Comprehensive suite of algorithms, libraries, and interfaces designed to standardize and streamline the process of interacting with large quantities of observational data (such as is provided by the RCMED) and conducting regional climate model evaluations.

Project name	Scale	Has a data model	Building description in model	IFC integration	Field connection – BMS protocols	Field connection - IoT	Status/Comments
Bemoss http://www.bemoss.org/ Virginia Polytecnic & STUARI	Building	Does not seem like.	Does not seem like.	Does not seem like.	yes (Zigbee API, HTTP/XML, MODBUS, BACNET, Smart energy, OpenADR)	Wifi, ZigBEE, RS-485, Ethernet	5 Contributors. Dormant for 2yrs Building Energy Management Open Source Software. BEMOSS™ is an open source operating system that is built upon VOLTTRON™ – a distributed agent platform developed by Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL).
openMAINT http://www.openmaint.org CMDBuild by Tecnoteca	Building	data model customization	Yes, based on BIMserver	Yes, based on BIMserver	Not apparently	SOAP and REST web services	Active. Manages movable assets (plants, technical elements, furniture, etc.), real estate (buildings, infrastructures in the area, etc.), related maintenance (scheduled, meter-based and breakdown), logistic, maintenance and economic activities.
Sentilo http://www.sentilo.io Barcelona City Council	Region	Does not seem like.	Does not seem like.	Does not seem like.	MAN, WAN, INET	HTTP/REST API	Active. 3 contributors. A layer that connects devices (data) and applications. Using open standards. Cross platform. Can also be used for the building level.
InterSCity http://interscity.org National Science and Technology Institute (INCT)	Region	Yes	No	No	No	HTTP/REST API	2 Contributors. Dormant 1 yr. A more academic trial which enables several application developments.
Kura IoT https://www.eclipse.org/kura/index.php Elipse Foundation	Device	Does not seem like.	Does not seem like.	Does not seem like.	Modbus, OPC-UA, S7	MQTT, REST	Active An extensible open source IoT Edge Framework based on Java/OSGi. Edge computing.

Project name	Scale	Has a data model	Building description in model	IFC integration	Field connection – BMS protocols	Field connection - IoT	Status/Comments
OpenHAB https://www.openhab.org/ OpenHAB foundation	Building	Yes (using Items)	Yes, need self-configuration of a room	Need self-configuration	Not apparently	Eclipse IoT Marketplace Integration, Other APIs	46 Contributors. Active. It is a self-customized system of systems. A vendor and technology agnostic open source automation software for your home
Open Energy Monitor https://openenergymonitor.org/	Device	Yes	For energy consuming and producing devices	Does not seem like.	Active	Yes	Robust Community Open source monitoring for understanding energy Exploring the context of renewable energy and zero carbon
IoTivity https://iotivity.org/ Open Connectivity Foundation	Device	Yes	Does not seem like.	Does not seem like.	Not apparently	REST, HTTP, Wifi, Ethernet	Active. An open source software framework enabling seamless device-to-device connectivity to address the emerging needs of the Internet of Things.
DSA http://www.iot-dsa.org/ DSA Initiative	Device	Yes	Does not seem like.	Does not seem like.	Many needs to be added	Many needs to be added	Active. A modular design enabling pluggable components to be created for any layer of an IoT implementation.
ACAEngine https://acaprojects.com/ ACAEngine	Building	Yes	Does not seem like.	Need to create from floor plan	For common equipment in buildings	REST, WIFI, etc	25 Contributors. Active. Also commercial, collaborates with partners like dimension data, etc. In essence a platform for building applications
IFC-HDF https://technical.buildingsmart.org/standards/ifc/ifc-formats/ Eindhoven University	Building	Yes, IFC	Yes, IFC	Conversion to and from IFC-SPF	SPARQL Query engine	SPARQL Query engine ¹	Initiating. Part of ifcOpenShell. IFC-HDF5 allows scalable integration of full IFC graphs and high frequency sensor data and large point cloud datasets

2.3 Platforms

In Section 2.1, market leaders in the intelligent buildings landscape according to Allied Market Research included well-known names such as Honeywell, ABB, Cisco Systems, Inc., Delta Controls, Honeywell International Inc., Intel Corporation, Johnson Controls, Legrand, Schneider Electric, Siemens AG, and United Technologies Corporation. In many cases, products and services for intelligent buildings start around the parent company product line. It makes sense that Schneider Electric (for example) would build software and cloud analytics around the data its hardware is collecting. A next progressive step is for these companies to enable the software and analytics they produce to be interoperable with hardware and sensors from other vendors. It is not common that large structures over time have hardware from different suppliers. A next progressive step is to become a marketplace for different products, services and value streams to cross. This is, to become a platform. If Allied Research is correct, then the current market landscape is dominated by IT companies and BMS providers. However, the it is already the case that the future landscape is changing Most energy suppliers are beginning to offer analytics surrounding energy consumption data, smart home and smart office concepts. There is also an increasing number of transversal platform products and services entering the market landscape (like BEMServer). Some of these are dedicated companies highlighted in the following examples.

Potential Competitors using a similar approach to BEMServer (proprietary or OS)

It is clear the market landscape will be competitive both in Apps/Modules and in Platforms. Figure 11 shows the landing page of SIMAXX¹⁵ which is in particular very close to what BEMServer is and does except that it is closed and proprietary. It is localized into the Dutch market where it is operating on over 300 tertiary building and is now positioning to expand internationally. Of the platforms we identified, SIMAXX does the best job communicating the concepts via their webpage and marketing.

Figure 11. Marketing on SIMAXX webpage

Figure 12. Simaxx homepage extract

Testimonials are used, the concept of "listening" to your building is used, the concept of "hands free" building service is communicated and the concept that it is normal to do this is also conveyed. An interactive dashboard of the platform functionalities is provided and various images are used to show the concepts of alerts and analytics. Of note, platform functionalities include indoor environmental quality (comfort and air quality) as does the BEMServer. For end users that would want closed and proprietary solution, SIMAXX is a good candidate. For clients that want an open approach or to develop a specific application for their purposes, BEMServer provides a more configurable option.

¹⁵ <https://www.simaxx.com/en/>

Another interesting platform is Facilio¹⁶. It starts first as a facility management platform and expands to asset management (multiple buildings in a central management platform) and also to sustainability (the concepts dealt within HIT2GAP). Facility management as a sector is more mature than building energy management and an interesting aspect of this platform is to combine sectors and offer bundled service offerings. To position against Facilio (assuming they have the same functionalities), the BEMServer would likely need to again position itself as more flexible, as open, and with better quality given if focuses on getting one aspect right.

Figure 14. Facilio Dashboard

Figure 13. VRM Clarity

A last platform highlighted is VRM Clarity¹⁷. It does a good job looking at multiple energy vectors (gas, water, district heating) and has a market point of entry of municipalities managing heat networks. To position against Clarity, BEMServer would stress its functionalities dedicated to tertiary buildings.

Two points in this competitor mapping exercise are clear. First, the BEMServer is not alone. Second, product differentiation becomes apparent. One can imagine potential clients assessing BEMServer against these various alternatives and the selection criteria they may have for any of the available options.

The Rise of Platforms and Multi-Sided Business Models

In considering business models for platforms, one must think beyond traditional software sale business models and toward multi-sides platform business models. Although such business models are relatively new, they are in fact, all around us.

A multi-sided platform business model is one in which value flows are bi-directional, multiple stakeholders participate in exchanges of value and one in which there are network effects (e.g. the more members there are that participate in the platform, the more value is created and passed within the value chain in both directions). A simple example is the Apple app. Store community. As more people use apps, the more developers are attracted to developing apps, which means the hardware can do more things, which leads to more hardware sales, which results in more people having the apps lowering pricing and increasing value across all stakeholder.

¹⁶ <https://facilio.com/>

¹⁷ <https://www.vrmtech.ie/>

BEMServer has the potential to empower or realize a multi-sided platform-based business model. The more that exciting modules are attracted to the platform and marketplace, the more value the platform will be able to deliver to building owners (and other clients), resulting in greater uptake of the platform, turnover and motivation for the realization of more platform functionalities. Value flows can also be anticipated to include the valorization of data. Just as prosumers can be paid for energy they generate via renewables or the flexibility they offer into smart grid business models (it is only recent that money flows in electric bill can be bi-directional), it is also to consider that datasets from buildings to platforms may provide additional business opportunities and value streams. Figure 15 shows the basic concept of a platform-based business model and Figure 16 is used to illustrate how common this business model type has become via well-known examples¹⁸.

Figure 15. Platform-based business model

Figure 16. Examples of Multi-Sided Platforms by Type

¹⁸ <https://www.innovationtactics.com/platform-business-model-complete-guide/> accessed 19 October 2018.

3 Project Results

This chapter provides a view on project results in three sections, the core platform, the exploitable results, and pointers to information surrounding those results.

3.1 The BEMServer Core Platform

One conceptual visualization of the BEMServer minimum viable product is shown in Figure 16. Modules are decoupled from the core platform and the connection to the building is not part of the BEMServer. From this minimum viable product, solution developers would customize a connection to the building (depending on if the BMS and information to aggregate is open, closed or hybrid) and select the series of modules that provide the functionalities desired by an end user.

The BEMServer core platform is Open Source (OS) and consists of:

- A storage solution making use of 3 different technologies, one for each of the following different data category handled:
 - Building data model
 - Timeseries
 - Events
- A data model (formal ontology) based on the well-consolidated IFC and Haystack standards called BEMOnt (<https://github.com/HIT2GAP-EU-PROJECT/BEMOnt>) which establishes a common data model and semantic knowledge management for buildings, including their interaction with occupants.
- Pre-processing functionalities so that all the data can be pre-processed before being stored, or before being presented to the third-party services.
 - Unit conversion
 - Time series resampling
 - Time series operation
 - Data cleansing.
- A presentation layer made of standard REST APIs to ease the integration of services. The complexity of the solution is fully hidden behind standards APIs. Additionally, BEMServer APIs are secured using a Role Based Access Control, which enables one to deploy a single instance of BEMServer for different sites and clients while ensuring no data could go to the wrong client.
- A visualisation tool based on an open source software for time series analytics (Grafana). It allows visualisation of raw and clean data collected in the platform.
- Calibro (<http://www.esru.strath.ac.uk/Programs/Calibro.htm>), an embedded Open Source module that performs automated calibration of any BPS model based on monitored data and taking into account input parameter uncertainties.

Figure 17. BEMServer Minimum Viable Product

With respect to workflow, the BEMServer core platform:

- receives on-site measured data (Unique API for data collection through direct connection to BMS or indirect connection using a M2M solution),
- pre-processes time series data (resampling, cleansing, unit conversion),
- handles semantic on the different measurements (using the BEMOnt data model),
- provides open APIs for 3rd party modules/services to access data,

- secures data access,
- performs automated calibration of any Building Performance Simulation (BPS) model based on monitored data and taking into account input parameter uncertainties,
- provides a visualization module that allows management and control of the raw and processed data using different available filters
- presents a uniform interface where client front-ends can be embedded,
- has the capability to load data from an IFC file (IFC reader module (used to import information from IFC files to the Core Platform)),
- receives and stores events or time-series generated by third-party modules.

A note on the connection to the building

The state of the art with respect to interoperability and data access has changed during the course of the project (more interoperable, more access to data). At the proposal stage, Plat.One was selected because it was a solution (among other existing ones) able to connect to most of the field buses. So, within the whole chain of data acquisition, Plat.One was the solution to address the connectivity to the field level. However, in the four pilot sites that occurred during the project, it was used at its "lowest capability level" in that it was used to connect to the data base in which the data were sent from the BMS. In this configuration, the BMS is set up to send the data to a DBB and we connect to the DBB to collect the data (this requires an interaction with the BMS provider which is not possible all the time). In other more complex configurations, Plat.One is also able to connect upstream, up to the field buses.

Currently, BEMServer does not have connectors for these different data access, but this is in the roadmap, because data access through FTP, HTTP, and Relational DBs is standard. Moreover, the HIT2GAP experience shows that in 90% of the situations, data would be available on a central server and one could consider this a "standard configuration".

The situation is more complex when the BMS is fully closed (i.e. there is no way to extract data from it). In this case, one would need to 'bypass' the BMS and read data through the field communication protocol. This is something Plat.One can do and something that may be able to be developed or found from other OS projects, such as OpenMUC developed by Fraunhofer (for a restricted list of protocols). This is the 'old-style' configuration, with old BMS.

The 'new-style' configuration will likely be a mix of open BMS and smart sensors (~IoT). IoT communication is also managed by specific protocols (like Lora). BEMServer cannot handle those yet, Plat.ONE can (and OpenMUC can't).

Regarding these 'old-style' and 'new-style' configuration, there is a security issue. A building manager would not easily accept someone to install some tool on their own/internal networks (those being sensors networks). This is why it is likely that 90% of the situations will likely involve a central node/server where the building manager keeps the control of its network and he is just exposing/duplicating the data in a machine that can be isolated for its networks. However, in this case there is a data latency issue and real time analytics/services lose the ability to work as well as developers and end-users would like them to work. These are not issues specific to BEMServer but to the building services sector overall and are open areas of development and research for proprietary teams and OS projects.

3.2 List of Exploitable Results

In total, the project closes with **23 exploitable results**. Four relate to the BEMServer platform, 12 to the developed modules, three to supporting technologies, two to knowledge and IP, and two to services. A summary of the ERs is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Final listing of HIT2GAP Exploitable Results

ER#	Metadata	Exploitable Result	Owner	Quick View Status
1	The Platform	BEMServer Platform	NBK	TRL 6/7. Validated at 4 pilots. Code and documentation are open access on GitHub. Calibro Module and Data Model ERs bundled.
2		BEMServer Open Source Project & Community	NBK	Launched. GNU Affero General Public License.
3		BEMServer Marketplace	NBK	Launched. Part of the BEMServer webpage.
4		BEMServer Webpage & Social Media	NBK	Launched and linked to OS project.
5	The Modules	Energy Management Module & Visualization	ENE	TRL9. Integrated into the BEMServer. Validated at 3 pilots. Commercial.
6		Fault Detection & Diagnosis PCA Module	UDG	TRL7. Integrated in BEMServer. User Instructions available. Validated at 4 pilots.
7		Load Forecasting Module	UDG	TRL7. Integrated in BEMServer. User Instructions available. Validated at 4 pilots.
8		REnSIM Module	CYR	TRL9. Integrated in BEMServer. User Instructions available. Validated at 1 pilot.
9		Fault Detection & Diagnosis – ML Module	FISE	TRL8. Integrated into the BEMServer. Validated at pilots.
10		BIMViewer / 3D Visualization Module Zutec Dimensions	ZUT	TRL9. Integrated into BEMServer. Validated at 2 pilots. Now commercial.
11		Gap Reasoner Module	FISE	TRL6. Integrated into BEMServer. Trialed at Nanogune. Further development needed.
12		ENIXO Semantic-driven behaviour simulation module	EGE	TRL7. Integrated into BEMServer. Tested at Challenger. Spinoff launched to carry on.
13		MODSCO Module (Reduced order building energy modelling)	NUIG	TRL6. Integrated into BEMServer. Tested at NUIG. Further development needed.
14		ESP-r Module (Indoor Environmental Quality)	UOS	Validated in 2 pilots.

ER#	Metadata	Exploitable Result	Owner	Quick View Status
15		WT-BeHave Module (Human Behaviour Management)	API	TRL9. First use in Central Asia. Integrated into BEMServer.
16		My Energy Assistant Visualization Module	INO	TRL8. Available for license.
17		Occupancy estimation and positioning module (Virtual Sensor)	EUR	TRL8. Can be applied to other sectors and is opportune for tech transfer.
18	Supporting technologies	Cylon Aspect Unitron Driver	CYL	TRL9. Used at NUIG pilot. Commercial. Has enabled 2 million euro sales.
19		MM-WSN Sensors, Gateways & System	TEK	TRL7. Partially tested at Nanogune. Items improved and continue development
20	Knowledge & IP	Use of reduced order models (ROM4EPC)	NUIG R2M	Body of work in simulation field that continues to advance.
21		Semantic model extending building modelling with user behaviour	EUR	Data model / ontology integrated into BEMOnt.
22	Service	Cylon legacy System Upgrades	CYL	Enables upgrade of existing Cylon clients. Strong demand.
23		Configuration or Use of BEMServer	NBK	Aggregates all potential services. Reflected in partner exploitation plans.

3.3 Final Stakeholder Events

Final Stakeholder Event at the Nanogune Office Building

The Nanogune final stakeholder event was held 13 June 2019 (Figure 18). It was given by GIR, NBK, UDG, IK4-TEK and EUR and had the aim to demonstrate the benefits and results of the Project to participants, who included: building management specialists from Bilbao and Zarauz, and to provide them with a tour of the facilities of Nanogune in San Sebastian.

Figure 18. Images from final stakeholder event at Nanogune

The day's presentations attracted a wide variety of questions from the audience. Some delegates, for instance, were keen to know more about the financial arrangements with regard to the modules and data platform. Delegates were also interested in how the modules interact with each other and share data and provide information/alerts to building users or to estates departments who might wish to analyse groups of buildings. Attendees also asked for more detail about module failures and fault detection. Questions even extended to questions about methodologies, variables and algorithms for forecasting. Some members of the audience asked how easy it will be to provide the necessary static information to enable the system to work for a particular building, including the setting up of models. The question and answer sessions also included some discussion of the relationship between users of buildings and energy consumptions. Overall feedback from the event was reported as:

- 1^o Congratulations for getting a platform where the different buildings, with their different systems and databases can be integrated and compatible with the new applications that are hosted within the BEM server.
- 2^o Congratulations for making it possible for different applications from different suppliers with different objectives to intercommunicate with each other.
- 3^o Although the project and the applications we show are very interesting, unfortunately the feeling is that they are not yet commercial applications with which they can sign a contract and start using them. When will they be?

Some of the questions were pointed and documenting them can better prepare for similar future questions.

As it has been thought to make compatible the store module that are free with the field hardware necessary for data collection, which involves a cost, due to each module will need to collect certain data and different for each module. How have we proposed to pass these costs on to the modules?

This question has two aspects the consortium has been working through, what is the process of system integration (now accounted for by this role in our exploitation framework) and that module user guidelines/technical specifications such that facility managers can quickly assess how their level of building readiness matches to the potential selection and use of any module or set of modules.

With regard to interoperability building, BEMServer and modules, a developer of a module may think that its module is useless if the BEMServer is not implemented in the building. This implies that the developer of the module should pay the implementation of the BEMServer? How can I provide or give a free service if it is necessary an implementation of the BEMServer that is alien to my module?

This question is from a developer's perspective (e.g. someone thinking they may be able to provide a module in the BEMServer environment). The question is not entirely clear but does show how stakeholders need help understanding the concept of an open source middleware that they can download for free if they want, that they will need to pay for if they need help and that has costs for customization and installation to be delivered to a building. It is not explicit, but it also raises questions for in what scenarios would modules deploy independent of the BEMServer and in what scenarios would they choose to bring BEMServer to a potential client. This issue is now part of our exploitation agreement in the recognition of referral fees.

Do customers need to have building modelers or is it automated?

This question is asking if a potential client will need to hire or grow new skills on staff to work with the BEMServer. The answer at this point in time is most likely yes. Implementing BEMServer is still a lot of work and over time this will become more efficient and over time knowledge transfer documentation and training materials will (need to) be developed. Several of the modules now have user guidelines and documentation related to the BEMServer is on the GitHub, but more work is required to enable solution developers to put it all together.

Is it possible to act directly on the equipment? If the BEMServer is fed with all kinds of data, such as how people have moved inside the building, could you send orders to the BMS to send slogans or other actions?

The answer is that no command can be sent to the BMS from the BEMServer. It shows that a user experience / GUI / dashboard (MyEnergy Assistant Module by INO) is something clients will likely want. It invites consideration of one way the functionality / value proposition of the BEMServer could be deepened in future development (BMS signals + GUI).

Do the modules interact with each other and how?

Good question that shows someone is understanding the concept and value BEMServer can bring. The answer is that the BEMOnt coupled to its data processing features and coupled to its APIs makes this possible, but an integrator/solution developer will need to put that together. It can be imagined that modules that for modules that are commonly put together, that OS routines/plugins would be developed and made available to facilitate solution building and this concept can be targeted objective within the OS project / community once this need starts to arise.

The BEMServer is fed from the static information BIM, is there the possibility to integrate data from the &D of the BIM, i.e. operating parameters? Is it automated to extract the information from the BIM and take it to the models, how does the system work if we change the BIM user who introduces the data under other procedures?

This question is not perfectly formulated but part of the answer is that extraction from the BIM Model/IFC file is automated. The question is interesting because it shows potential in connecting the world of BIM and the world of BEM which is why we coupled the name BEMServer to the more known environment and OS project BIMServer. So, it is good to receive such a question.

Final Stakeholder Event at the NUIG Alice Perry Building

The NUIG final stakeholder event was held on 29 August 2019 (Figure 19). It was given by NUIG, CYL, R2M, UOS, ENE, and ZUT. In contrast to the Nanogune event, it occurred on the backside of summer allowing for the maximum available time for pilot activities to mature but attendance to events in August is difficult. Event participation was between 20-30 persons. The key targeted event participants were the facility management staff at NUIG (such profiles are not always easy to schedule). The event was approved as an Engineers Ireland West Region CPD event (continuing professional development) for 2.5 hours enabling use of their logo and advertising on their network channels (website + newsletter). In addition, the event was broadcast via live stream but for which we had no way of assessing / counting logins. However, the intent was to make it a public event available to the widest possible audience¹⁹.

Figure 19. Promotion for the NUIG Final Stakeholder Event

The workshop was preceded in the afternoon by a one-on-one meeting with the facility management staff to present again the results of ongoing implementations and to get their feedback on the system to date. The agenda for the workshop was as follows:

29th August 2019 – 17:00h to 19:30h

Chaired: Marcus M. Keane – NUIG Lecturer and Director of IRUSE

Alice Perry Engineering Building. University Road Galway. Room G047 – Ground Floor

17:00h - Reception at the Alice Perry Building Foyer. Introduction by Dr. Marcus M. Keane - NUIG

17:00h - Tour of the Building: Case Studies

17:30h - Presentations: 19:00h - Panel Discussion: “The Future of Energy Management”

¹⁹ https://www.eventbrite.ie/e/the-future-of-energy-management-launch-of-bemserver-the-worlds-premier-open-source-building-energy-tickets-70077857759?utm_term=eventurl_text#

- Overview of Pilot Activities in HIT2GAP / BEM Server – Tom Messervey (R2M)BMS solution and open platforms – Paul Cowling (Cylon);
- Zutec – BIM tools and BMS empowering – Brendan O’Riordan & Liam Stanley (Zutec);
- UoS – Dealing with indoor environmental quality issues in existing building – Daniel Costola (University of Strathclyde);
- NUIG – ModSCO. Easy tool for energy models – Luis M. Blanes (NUIG);
- Enerit – Energy Management tool and case studies – John Cunningham (Enerit);
- Lessons Learned from the HIT2GAP case studies – Daniel Costola;
- Panel Discussion
- 19:30h - Refreshments provided

The main benefit of the event and workshop in the afternoon was time together with the NUIG Facility Management staff. They gave us some views into what their daily routine looks like and also provided some candid remarks.

- Comfort: yes of course, but nobody is ever really happy in Galway and people are hot and cold the same place at the same time.
- The list of things to do at any given time (FM actions) is beyond what the FM staff can handle. If the BEMServer can help manage, mitigate, reduce or direct elsewhere stimulus on the FM staff, this would be value added.
- Their number one priority after good working order health and safety is meeting the energy efficiency targets the campus has set.

During the panel discussion, we asked the facility management staff: What would it take to get them to keep using BEMServer after the project? What did they find most useful? What is the next step? Responses included:

- They see a lot of potential in the tool. Such approaches are a part of the future.
- Working with the project has been a good experience. It forced them to do housecleaning. They had to straighten up some of their documentation to get us the answers we needed. Doing that they found problems and made fixes. The fault detection module found a problem with an AHU that they would have otherwise missed and that got fixed.
- They are happy to provide their buildings anytime and to collaborate with the engineering department/students on these topics. We discussed potentially linking BEMServer concepts to coursework and the ability to support thesis topics as well.
- We should have such events in Dublin. We can attract a wider audience.
- There is a council of Facility Managers for Irish Universities. We should present BEMServer there.

Adding to the BEMServer Value Proposition

Discussions always contain "can you do this?" or "could you do that?" The strategic roadmap at proprietary companies is often set, decided and resourced for the next 2-3 years. Only major market forces will cause any deviation to that roadmap and there is little to no room for co-creation. This is in sharp contrast to the BEMServer approach which starts from the complete other direction. What type of solution is right for you? Let's build it. Through our workshops and panel discussions, we better understood the additional value our approach and methodology bring.

3.4 Other Results

The project has done considerable work to make its results available to building stakeholders, developers and to the public overall. Sources of information include:

- The project website (www.hit2gap.eu)
- The BEMServer website (www.bemserver.org)
- The BEMServer GitHub (<https://github.com/HIT2GAP-EU-PROJECT/BEMServer>)
- The HIT2GAP Twitter Feed (<https://twitter.com/HIT2GAP>)
- The HIT2GAP LinkedIn Group (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12099320/>)
- The BEMServer LinkedIn Group (<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/bemserver/>)
- On the EU Cordis Portal: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/198379/factsheet/en>

Figure 20. Project Webpage at www.hit2gap.eu – don't miss it.

Public deliverables are each available on the project website. These are shown in the following listing. Special attention is drawn to the D5.3 (Pilot Results) and D5.4 (Knowledge Transfer).

- D1.1 Module Methodology Overview (linking Hit2Gap and adding value...)
- D1.8 Data Management Plan
- D1.9 Synthesis of the Hit2Gap methodology
- D2.1 Synthesis on available for the connection of the Hit2Gap platform to the existing BMS
- D2.2 Synthesis report on the benchmark conducted in the field of new data fields in offices
- D3.6 Module Descriptions
- D4.2 Protocols, rules and guidelines for the integration of elementary modules by third-parties
- D5.3 Pilot Results
- D5.4 Knowledge Transfer – lessons learned in Hit2Gap
- D6.3 Market Analysis & Replication Plan
- D7.2 Market communication strategy
- D7.3 Public communication materials
- D7.4 Dissemination and awareness activities

4 Replication Plan

This chapter provides information related to the next steps for the development and exploitation of the BEMServer and replication

4.1 Approach

BEMServer as an Open Source Project

The HIT2GAP EU project has rebranded itself into the BEMServer with respect to the middleware platform and has created "The World's Premier Open Source Building Energy Management Platform." In doing so, the foreground becomes public and opened to developers, integrators and end users worldwide. Two key messages are shown in Figure 21 and Figure 22.

BEMServer
Making sense of your building data

What is BEMServer?

BEMServer is an **open source** solution enabling building stakeholders to deploy a modular, scalable and secure Building Energy Management System by **downloading the code directly** or working with the **BEMServer community**.

BEMServer has an existing set of services via its modules and new modules can be developed by 3rd party developers anytime. For building owners and managers through BEMServer, **building data gain meaning and empower building actors** with new services to optimize energy consumption and comfort.

An open source solution

Up to
25%
energy savings

Figure 21. Key Message - Extract from the BEMServer Webpage

What you can do with BEMServer

Facility Managers	Module Developers	Contributors
<p>Collect all your data in one central solution: BMS data, weather, occupants feedbacks, building descriptive data, contextual data).</p>	<p>Forget about Issues collecting on-site data and focus on bringing added-value to your clients.</p>	<p>Get into a fully tested and deployed code, and be part of an open project to build up the solution you want.</p>
<p>Choose the right module for your need to assist you in your daily job.</p>	<p>Use meaningful data and do not waste time wondering which data you are handling, thanks to our data model based on the IFC and Haystack standards, and to REST APIs.</p>	<p>Accelerate Innovation in building monitoring with your own proposals.</p>
Your energy monitoring solution	Your backbone solution	The place to join forces

Figure 22. Targeting Stakeholders: Extract from the BEMServer webpage

License Type

BEMServer has been published under the GNU Affero General Public License.

<https://choosealicense.com/licenses/agpl-3.0/>

A summary description of this license is reproduced from TLDRLegal in the following text and image²⁰:

"The AGPL license differs from the other GNU licenses in that it was built for network software. You can distribute modified versions if you keep track of the changes and the date you made them. As per usual with GNU licenses, you must license derivatives under AGPL. It provides the same restrictions and freedoms as the GPLv3 but with an additional clause which makes it so that source code must be distributed along with web publication. Since web sites and services are never distributed in the traditional sense, the AGPL is the GPL of the web."

Can	Cannot	Must
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Commercial Use ▶ Modify ▶ Distribute ▶ Place Warranty 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Sublicense ▶ Hold Liable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Include Copyright ▶ Include License ▶ State Changes ▶ Disclose Source ▶ Include Install Instructions

Figure 23. GNU AGPL summary information

Open source does not mean altruistic. To the contrary, revenue will be required to maintain and further develop the BEMServer core platform to its full potential. The business model surrounding the BEMServer and anticipated future revenue streams are as follows:

- **Public R&D Funding:** Future national or international funded research.
- **Private R&D Funding:** BEMServer provides a platform in which 3rd parties can have research questions answered. BEMServer is open for business.
- **Consulting** for BEMServer customization: Future adopters will likely want to build on top of the BEMServer. In many cases, consulting support will be desired.
- **Maintenance, Hosting and Support for Businesses:** Companies that build solutions on top of BEMServer are likely to request maintenance, hosting and troubleshooting support.
- **Maintenance, Hosting and Support for Buildings** in the event that BEMServer implementations are hosted and maintained by the platform owner instead of onsite.
- **Training:** Software products that have success eventually develop training revenue streams.
- **BEMServer Implementations:** especially for early implementations, there will be the need and opportunity to develop and deliver BEMServer Projects.

BEMServer Marketplace / Module Store

The BEMServer marketplace is where solution developers can purchase and download the modules they want to use. The marketplace is available at <https://www.bemserver.org/end-users/modules->

²⁰ [https://tldrlegal.com/license/gnu-affero-general-public-license-v3-\(agpl-3.0\)](https://tldrlegal.com/license/gnu-affero-general-public-license-v3-(agpl-3.0))

[already-developed/](#) and is populated with the modules shown in Table 3 each developed within the HIT2GAP project.

Table 3. Modules ready for use at BEMServer

ER#	Exploitable Result	Owner	Targeted End Users
5	Energy Management Module & Visualization	ENE	Energy managers or facility managers implementing ISO50001
6	Fault Detection & Diagnosis PCA Module	UDG	Facility managers
7	Load Forecasting Module	UDG	Smart grid, renewables and demand response
8	REnSIM Module	CYR	
9	Fault Detection & Diagnosis – ML Module	FISE	Facility managers
10	BIMViewer / 3D Visualization Module Zutec Dimensions	ZUT	BIM Users (large construction projects and trending to smaller projects/public buildings)
12	ENIXO semantic-driven behavior simulation module	EGE	Facility managers with express interest in IAQ / behavior faults, wellness certifications or niche structures
14	ESP-r Module (Indoor Environmental Quality)	UOS	
15	WT-BeHave Module (Human Behaviour Management)	API	
16	My Energy Assistant Visualization Module	INO	Facility managers and building occupants

The common link between these buildings is tertiary buildings, facility managers and smarter buildings in their operational phase. Module developers are free to choose the type of license associated with their module and cost structure (license, SAAS, free, other). Like other platforms, the marketplace will run on a "survival of the fittest" concept and the best modules with respect to value and functionality will rise to the top.

The current version of the marketplace is a first version. This first version:

- Uses a one-level page structure on the BEMServer webpage
- Is reachable and pointed to from several other parts of the BEMServer environment with module descriptions and/or testimonials
- Publishes modules in a similar format
- Clusters modules by type (Monitoring, Visualization, Energy Control, Energy Behavior)
- Uses partner logos instead of product logos
- Distinguishes between modules ready for use and modules under development considering also evaluation during pilot activities
- Hangs user guidelines
- Provides a point of contact
- Provides screenshots and/or videos where available.

A next important step is to upgrade to a second version of the marketplace which will be more commercial in nature. Figure 24, Figure 25 and Figure 26 provide views of what the second version will likely look more like. Two-levels of pages (one quick view with clustered modules/apps and a second level dedicated specifically to the module), the use of product logos, the use of screenshots on the second level page to show what the module does, written descriptions, the presence of a rating system, the display of cost, information for support, the ability to download, a counter for the

number of downloads, the ability to comment/read reviews (in some environments), tours and demos (certain environments), the logos of featured customers using that app (certain environments), and the availability of documentation regarding the module/app (certain environments). These are next steps for the BEMServer environment.

Figure 24. SAP App Center²¹

Figure 25. BIMserver.center Store²²

Figure 26. Second level page for an app on the BIMserver.center store

²¹ <https://www.sapappcenter.com/home>

²² https://bimserver.center/bim_store.asp

4.2 Strategic Roadmap Forward

The BEMServer journey is just beginning and now anyone can join the development process. Table 4 documents next steps for the development, marketing, communication and use of the BEMServer. With respect to continued development, a prioritized list of next actions has been documented which includes things such as improvement of the user experience and administrative functions, improvement of data cleansing, normalization and pre-processing as this benefits the analytics of all modules and data quality is often a challenge to deal with, and development of open source solutions for building connectivity to reduce any reliance on alternative high-cost options.

Table 4. Near term BEMServer roadmap

Strategic Area	Objectives	Actions
BEMServer Continued Development	To deepen the functionalities and value proposition of the BEMServer core platform.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Run and maintain the BEMServer OS project • Improve BEMServer marketplace • Submit new R&D Proposals • Continue internal funded development
Marketing & Communication	Create new opportunities for BEMServer use and development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continued publishing of BEMServer success stories • Continued participation in events • Continued delivery of BEMServer key messages across all dissemination and communication channels • Marketing to reinforce Development and Business Objectives • Target additional stakeholders
Business Development	Secure future revenue streams and project pipeline to ensure long-term commercial viability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop additional POC, demo/test/pilot together with module providers • Solicit industrially funded research • Solicit next early adopter implementations • Solicit developers to participate in the BEMServer marketplace • Continue business development visits • Seek partnership opportunities • Monitor incentives and national programs

4.3 Roles and Remuneration Framework

Anyone can use, develop and make business on top of the BEMServer in accordance with the terms and conditions of the license. Figure 27 and Figure 28 are used to show how that gets done by making clear the roles and responsibilities of each actor involved in future BEMServer implementations. From roles and responsibilities, remuneration follows. Platform costs (when facilitated by the platform owner) and module costs are largely fixed. Solution integration and business development costs will depend on the type, size and complexity of the implementation. Referral fees are optional and will depend on the business practices of the organizations involved. One actor may assume multiple roles and it can be the case that actors negotiate different responsibilities than those depicted. Nevertheless, these figures provide the starting framework to get it done.

Figure 27. Roles in a BEMServer Implementation

Figure 28. Responsibilities of Roles in a BEMServer Implementation

5 Conclusions

This report concludes and makes public the key aspects of replication planning for the HIT2GAP project and BEMServer middleware platform. Central themes to our exploitation strategy are:

- The core platform is open source and available for all stakeholders
- Open source and intelligent buildings are megatrends, ask us about it
- The journey is just beginning – join us
- The more persons that use the platform, the more value the platform will bring and as result, the cycle will continue (network effects)
- Through solutions like the BEMServer, we can improve the performance of our buildings in the operational phase and contribute to meeting sustainability targets

For the latest information on where we are today, visit www.bemserver.org. See you there.

